

Cluster and Conquer: The Use of Clustering-Triggered Emission Materials in Photodynamic Therapy

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Methods

1. Synthesis of poly(PA-alt-COExo)

In the glovebox, toluene (5 mL), 4-dimethylaminopyridine (DMAP) (31 mg, 254.5 μmol), carvone-based epoxide (COExo) (846 mg, 5.09 mmol) and phthalic anhydride (PA) (754 mg, 5.09 mmol) were placed into a 10 mL Schlenk equipped with a small stir bar. The Schlenk was then taken out of the glovebox and placed in a preheated oil bath under a nitrogen atmosphere at 95 °C for 24 h. Once the polyester was obtained, the viscous mixture was dissolved in the minimum amount of dichloromethane, precipitated with an excess of methanol and, finally, filtered off and dried to constant weight to afford a white solid (1.47 g, 92%).

2. Characterization of Purity of poly(PA-alt-COExo)

After appropriate dilution of the solid (1.12 mg of purified solid was dissolved in 3 mL 1:1:1 (v/v/v) H₂O:MeOH:THF), Liquid chromatography coupled to high-resolution mass spectrometry (LC-HRMS) was employed for the analysis of artifacts and impurities. A UHPLC-Q-Orbitrap-MS/MS analysis was conducted utilising a Vanquish™ UHPLC system (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Carlsbad, CA, USA) connected to a Q-Exactive mass spectrometer (Thermo Scientific) with heated electrospray ionisation. The separation was conducted on a Zorbax Eclipse plus-C18 Rapid column (2.1 mm x 150 mm, 1.8 μm) (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, MA, USA). The mobile phase consisted of water (A) and methanol (B), both of which had 0.1% formic acid. A flow rate of 0.3 mL min⁻¹ was selected, with a gradient starting at 10% B, then linearly increasing to 95% B at 17.0 min; remaining constant at 95% B until 5.0 min; decreasing to 10% B at 20.0 min; and being maintained constant for re-equilibration. The column was maintained at a temperature of 30 °C, and the injection volume was 1 μL .

The mass spectrum data was acquired in both positive and negative ion mode through full MS and higher energy collisional dissociation (HCD) data-dependent MS/MS by the UHPLC-Q-Orbitrap-MS/MS, which was equipped with a control software (Xcalibur, version 4.2.27). The scan parameters were set as follows: mass-to-charge ratio (m/z) scan range, 170 to 2500 Da; resolution, 70,000; automatic gain control (AGC) target, 3×10^6 ; maximum injection time, 100 ms. The following parameters were employed for the heated electrospray ionisation source (HESI

source): spray voltage, 3.0 kV for ESI⁻ and 3.5 kV for ESI⁺; sheath gas flow rate, 40 arb; auxiliary gas flow rate, 10 arb; sweep gas flow rate, 0 arb; capillary temperature, 320 °C; s-lens RF level, 50; and auxiliary gas heater temperature, 350 °C. A data-dependent scan (dd-MS2) was employed to obtain high-quality MS2 data. The five most intense precursors were automatically selected for MS/MS fragmentation by HCD. The parameters of the dd-MS2 method were as follows: resolution, 17,500; AGC target, 2×10^5 ; maximum IT, 100 ms; loop count, 5; isolation window, 1 m/z. The Normalised Collision Energy (NCE) was set at 15 and 30 V.

3. Photophysical and photochemical characterization

All the solvents used for the photophysical, and photochemical characterization have spectroscopic grade or MiliQ water. UV-Vis absorption spectra were recorded using a Varian Cary 6000i spectrometer (Varian, Palo Alto, CA, USA). Fluorescence emission spectra were recorded using a Spex Fluoromax-4 spectrofluorometer (Horiba Jobin-Yvon, Edison, NJ, USA).

¹O₂ generation was studied by time-resolved near-infrared phosphorescence using a customised Fluotime 200 time-resolved spectrophotometer (PicoQuant, Berlin, Germany).[35,36] A diode-pumped Nd:YAG laser (FTSS355-Q, Crystal Laser, Berlin, Germany) working at a 1-kHz repetition rate (0.5 μJ per pulse) was used for excitation at 355 nm. A 1064 nm rugate notch filter (Edmund Optics) and an uncoated SKG-5 filter (CVI Laser Corporation) were placed in the laser path to remove any residual NIR emission. The ¹O₂ phosphorescence emitted by the sample was filtered with a 1100 nm long-pass filter (Edmund Optics) and later by a narrow bandpass filter at 1275 nm (BK-1270-70-B, bk Interferenzoptik). A thermoelectric-cooled NIR-sensitive photomultiplier tube assembly (H10330C-45-C3, Hamamatsu Photonics, Hamamatsu, Japan) was used as detector. Photon counting was achieved with a multichannel scaler (NanoHarp 250, PicoQuant, Berlin, Germany). The time dependence of the ¹O₂ phosphorescence with the signal intensity $S(t)$ is described by Equation 1, in which τ_T and τ_Δ are the lifetimes of the photosensitizer triplet state and of ¹O₂ respectively, and $S(0)$ is a preexponential parameter proportional to the ¹O₂ formation quantum yield (Φ_Δ). For the methodology for determining Φ_Δ , please check Figure S4. The used reference photosensitizer is phenalenone ($\Phi_\Delta = 1$).[53-55]

$$S(t) = S(0) \times \left(\frac{\tau_{\Delta}}{\tau_{\Delta} - \tau_T} \right) \times (e^{-t/\tau_{\Delta}} - e^{-t/\tau_T}) \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

Transient absorption kinetics (ΔAbs) were acquired using a home-built nanosecond laser flash photolysis system.[56] Briefly, the sample was excited by a 355 nm Q-switched Nd:YAG Laser (Surelite I-10, Continuum) with right-angle geometry. The analysing beam is composed by a Xe lamp (PTI, 75 W) in combination with a dual-grating monochromator (mod. 101, PTI) coupled to a UV-Vis radiation detector (PTI 710). The observation wavelength was selected to 380 nm which corresponds to the ground state bleaching of the generated molecular clusters. The signal was fed to a Lecroy WaveSurfer 454 oscilloscope for digitizing and averaging (10 shots) and finally transferred to a PC for data storage and analysis.

4. Photoantimicrobial studies

Three different strains, one gram-positive, *Staphylococcus aureus* (*S. aureus*, ATCC 29213) and two gram-negative, *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*, ATCC 35218) and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (*P. aeruginosa*, ATCC 27853) were used in this study. Briefly, the culture media used for growing the cells was Tryptic Soy Broth (TSB). The PDT treatment protocol was adapted from Ref.[57]. The strains were grown overnight at 37 ± 1 °C in an orbital shaker at 60 rpm under aerobic conditions. Then, 100 μL of the culture were grown in 10 mL of fresh TSB until reaching an optical density of 0.18, measured at 600 nm. These OD_{600} values corresponds to bacterial concentration of 10^7 CFU/mL for *S. aureus*, and 10^8 CFU/mL for *E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa*. After that, bacteria were harvested by centrifugation (4000 rpm, 10 minutes) and resuspended in the same volume of sterile PBS or deuterated-PBS. Then, the adequate concentration of the polymer dissolved in DMSO (always $\leq 1\%$) was added to the bacterial suspension and let incubate for 60 minutes in dark conditions. After, the bacterial suspension was irradiated using a violet LED (Figure S9) until reach the adequate light fluence (27 and 80 J/cm^2), using a light irradiance of 15.2 mW/cm^2 . 1 mL of the bacterial suspension was kept unirradiated and used as dark control. After the PDT treatment, the bacterial suspensions were diluted by a factor of 10, until reaching a 10^{-6} dilution

factor. Finally, 10 μL of every dilution were spread on Tryptic Soy Agar and were incubated aerobically at 37 ± 1 °C. The colony forming units (CFU) were counted after 24 hours of incubation and the dilution factor was considered.

To study the interaction between the CTEgen material and bacteria, we used the same three bacterial strains. The bacteria were grown until they reached an OD_{600} of 0.2. The bacteria were then harvested by centrifugation (4000 rpm, 10 minutes) and washed thrice with the same volume of sterile PBS. Next, the bacteria were incubated aerobically at 37 ± 1 °C for 1 hour with CTEgen material at a concentration of 150 mg/L. The CTEgen was previously dissolved in DMSO, maintaining an overall DMSO concentration of 1%. To account for the autofluorescence of bacteria, we also incubated control samples of each bacterium with 1% DMSO but without CTEgen. After incubation, the cells were harvested by centrifugation, washed once, and resuspended in PBS. Finally, we measured the fluorescence ($\lambda_{\text{Exc}} = 355$ nm) of the bacterial suspension for both the control samples and the samples incubated with CTEgen.

Experimental evidence supporting the production of singlet oxygen by photoexcitation of the polymer (CTEgen material)

Throughout the text, we present up to seven solid pieces of evidences that collectively provide strong support for the production of $^1\text{O}_2$ by the polymer upon photoexcitation:

- 1) LC-MS analysis provided strong evidence that the only source of the observed light-interacting mechanism (absorption, emission, or other relaxation processes), are the oligo(PA-alt-COExo)-related species (Figures S1,S2 and Tables S1,S2).
- 2) We observed the formation and decay of $^1\text{O}_2$ through its near-infrared phosphorescence, centered at 1270 nm (Figure S4). This spectroscopic fingerprint is specific to $^1\text{O}_2$. Therefore, if the only chromophore(s) in the solution are the different clusters of the polymer (with the exclusion of impurities, as detailed in point 1), the observed $^1\text{O}_2$ phosphorescence is related to the excitation of such clusters.
- 3) The production of $^1\text{O}_2$ increases non-linearly with the polymer concentration (Figure S5) in both THF and H₂O suspensions, which is a key characteristic of a CTE-mediated process.
- 4) We studied the triplet state kinetics of these CTEgens using transient absorption spectroscopy. The triplet state is quenched by molecular oxygen, exhibiting a bimolecular quenching rate larger than $1 \times 10^9 \text{ M}^{-1} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ (Figure S7).
- 5) The formation (rise) lifetime of $^1\text{O}_2$ phosphorescence corresponds with the triplet state decay lifetime observed by transient absorption spectroscopy (TAS) in both THF ($0.3 \pm 0.1 \mu\text{s}$ ($^1\text{O}_2$ phosphorescence) and $0.3 \pm 0.1 \mu\text{s}$ (TAS), Figure 3A) and H₂O ($6.8 \pm 1.5 \mu\text{s}$ ($^1\text{O}_2$ phosphorescence) and $9.6 \pm 2.0 \mu\text{s}$ (TAS), Figure 3B) suspensions. This experimental evidence demonstrate that the triplet state is the precursor of $^1\text{O}_2$ formation.
- 6) Consistent with points 4 and 5, the observed $^1\text{O}_2$ phosphorescence disappears when oxygen is replaced by argon (see the added purple line in Figure S4).
- 7) The formation and escapement of $^1\text{O}_2$ from the polymer matrix has also been indirectly demonstrated by trapping it with a suitable selective $^1\text{O}_2$ chemical acceptor, such as tryptophan (Figure S10).

Figure S1. Overlapped LC-HRMS(+) Total ion chromatograms of oligo(PA-alt-COExo) dissolved in H₂O/MeOH/THF (1:1:1 (v/v/v)) (green trace) and the blank solvent used (H₂O/MeOH/THF (1:1:1 (v/v/v))) (red trace).

Peak (n)	Retention time (min)	Experimental m/z ($[M+Na]^+$)	Calculated m/z ($[M+Na]^+$)	Annotated elemental composition	(Δ) Elemental composition	($\Delta m/z$) ($n - (n-1)$)	(PA-COExo) units added to COExo	Error (ppm)	Relative abundance (peak area)
1	13.75	521.2137	521.21459	C ₂₈ H ₃₄ O ₈ Na ⁺	-	-	1	-1.71	0.610
2	15.81	835.3269	835.33001	C ₄₆ H ₅₂ O ₁₃ Na ⁺	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ O ₅	314.1132	2	-3.72	1
3	16.94	1149.4430	1149.44544	C ₆₄ H ₇₀ O ₁₈ Na ⁺	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ O ₅	314.1161	3	-2.09	0.474
4	17.65	1463.5581	1463.56086	C ₈₂ H ₈₈ O ₂₃ Na ⁺	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ O ₅	314.1151	4	-1.89	0.144
5	18.08	1777.6742	1777.67628	C ₁₀₀ H ₁₀₆ O ₂₈ Na ⁺	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ O ₅	314.1161	5	-1.17	0.048
6	18.56	2091.7908	2091.79171	C ₁₁₈ H ₁₂₄ O ₃₃ Na ⁺	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ O ₅	314.1166	6	-0.43	0.011
7	18.88	2405.9070	2405.90713	C ₁₃₆ H ₁₄₂ O ₃₈ Na ⁺	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ O ₅	314.1162	7	0.01	0.006

Table S1. Accurate mass measurements of oligo(PA-alt-COExo) using LC-ESI(+)-HRMS(+).

Figure S2. MS/MS spectra of the sodium adducts of, **a)** COExo-(PA-COExo)₁ and **b)** COExo-(PA-COExo)₂.

COExo-(PA-COExo) ₁			
Experimental m/z value	Calculated m/z value	Proposed fragment structure	Fragmentation type
521.2137	521.2146		---
355.1142	355.1152		Loss of COExo through epoxide formation
207.0987	207.0992		Loss of PA-COExo moiety through intramolecular cyclization
COExo-(PA-COExo) ₂			
Experimental m/z value	Calculated m/z value	Proposed fragment structure	Fragmentation type
835.3269	835.3300		---
503.2028	503.2028		Loss of PA-COExo unit through elimination

355.1143	355.1152		Loss of COExo through epoxide formation (cascade reaction)
337.1038	337.1046		Loss of COExo-PA-COExo unit through intramolecular cyclization.
207.0989	207.0992		Sodiated COExo diol unit released through intramolecular cyclization.
149.0958	149.0961		Secondary fragmentation from 503.2028Da ion through simple inductive cleavage of the associated ester bond.
107.0853	107.0855		Loss of ketene from 149.0958Da fragment.

Table S2. Structures and tentative formation mechanisms of the most relevant fragments observed in the MS/MS spectra of COExo-(PA-COExo)₁ and COExo-(PA-COExo)₂.

Figure S3. Absorption spectra of the polymer in H₂O (A) and THF:H₂O mixtures (B) acquired using a sphere integration system. The polymer concentration in panel B is 0.25 g/L. Please note that the absorption spectra (obtained using an integrating sphere) shown in panels A and B have the same concentration as the extinction spectra (a combination of absorption and scattering spectra) shown in panels B and C of Figure 1 in the main text. The differences between the extinction and absorption spectra are attributed to the scattering contribution. The absorption spectra of the polymer solution in THF were not acquired using the integrating sphere system because the solution was not turbid, making both spectra equivalent.

Figure S4. Spectroscopic proofs that the observed NIR emission is specifically due to the formation of $^1\text{O}_2$ upon 355 nm pulsed laser excitation of the CTE polymer suspended in tetrahydrofuran. (A): Time-resolved NIR emission at different observation wavelength. Notably, the observed NIR phosphorescence spectrum corresponds to the spectroscopic fingerprint of $^1\text{O}_2$ phosphorescence. The emission of $^1\text{O}_2$ is centered around 1270 nm, with a tail extending from 1200 to 1350 nm. (B): Time-resolved 1270 nm emission of the CTE polymer suspended in air-saturated (black) and argon-saturated (purple) tetrahydrofuran. Notably, the 1275 nm phosphorescence disappears, when air is replaced by argon, confirming that the observed emission is due to $^1\text{O}_2$ phosphorescence.

Figure S5. Dependence of $^1\text{O}_2$ phosphorescence intensity (S_0) with the polymer concentration dissolved in tetrahydrofuran (A) or suspended in water (B). $\lambda_{\text{Exc}} = 355 \text{ nm}$; $\lambda_{\text{Obs}} = 1270 \text{ nm}$.

Figure S6. Determination of $^1\text{O}_2$ formation quantum yield (Φ_Δ) for the polymer dissolved in tetrahydrofuran. To determine Φ_Δ , we compare the dependence of the $^1\text{O}_2$ phosphorescence intensity (S_0) on the sample absorbance factor ($1-10^{-A}$) for the CTE polymer with the same dependence for a reference photosensitizer phenalenone ($\Phi_\Delta = 1$; PN) in tetrahydrofuran. $\lambda_{\text{Exc}} = 355$ nm; $\lambda_{\text{Obs}} = 1270$ nm. The time dependence of the $^1\text{O}_2$ phosphorescence with the signal intensity $S(t)$ is described by Equation S1, where τ_T and τ_Δ are the lifetimes of the photosensitizer triplet state and of $^1\text{O}_2$, respectively, and $S(0)$ is a quantity proportional to Φ_Δ as shown in Equation S2; κ is a proportionality constant, which includes electronic and geometric factors, k_R is the $^1\text{O}_2$ radiative rate constant, E is the incident laser energy, and A is the sample absorbance at 355 nm.

$$S(t) = S(0) \frac{\tau_\Delta}{\tau_\Delta - \tau_T} \left(e^{-\frac{t}{\tau_\Delta}} - e^{-\frac{t}{\tau_T}} \right) \quad \text{Eq. S1}$$

$$S(0) = \kappa k_r \Phi_\Delta E (1 - 10^{-A}) \quad \text{Eq. S2}$$

Figure S7. Role of molecular oxygen concentration on the fate of CTE triplet excited states in tetrahydrofuran. Left: Transient absorption traces in argon-saturated (top); air-saturated (middle) and oxygen-saturated (bottom) tetrahydrofuran. $\lambda_{\text{Exc}} = 355 \text{ nm}$; $\lambda_{\text{Obs}} = 380 \text{ nm}$. The kinetic traces show a monoexponential decay with lifetimes of $40 \mu\text{s}$ (argon-saturated), $0.3 \mu\text{s}$ (air-saturated), and $0.2 \mu\text{s}$ (oxygen-saturated). Right: Pseudo Stern Volmer plot for the three tested oxygen concentrations (red circles and dotted line). The oxygen concentration for each experimental condition has been calculated according with Henry's law with a Henry constant of $0.14 \text{ mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}\cdot\text{kPa}^{-1}$.^[S1] Of note, a non-linear Stern-Volmer relationship is obtained, suggesting that the cluster excited states can be quench through a dynamic and static mechanism. As a visual aid, dashed black lines corresponding to quenching constants (k_q) of 1×10^9 , 5×10^8 , and $2 \times 10^8 \text{ M}^{-1}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ are added to the right panel.

Figure S8. Changes on the absorbance, fluorescence, τ_T and τ_Δ (top to bottom) over increasing the polymer concentration in tetrahydrofuran (THF).

Figure S9. Singlet oxygen phosphorescence kinetic traces of 0.5 g/L polymer suspended in D₂O and H₂O (red and blue lines, respectively). The black line is the result of fitting Eq.1 (main text) to both kinetic traces as well as their corresponding residual analysis (bottom). $\lambda_{\text{Exc}} = 355 \text{ nm}$; $\lambda_{\text{Obs}} = 1270 \text{ nm}$.

The suspension of the polymer in water forms two different phases: 1) the interior of the aggregated polymer, which is hydrophobic, and 2) the surrounding aqueous environment, which is hydrophilic. The relaxation of ¹O₂ is highly sensitive to the chemical properties of the medium, resulting in different decay rate constants for each phase (k_{pol} and k_{aq} , respectively). However, if the entrance and exit constants of ¹O₂ between the two phases are much larger than the ¹O₂ decay rate constants within the two individual phases, the observed apparent ¹O₂ decay is expected to follow a monoexponential function. According to the kinetic model developed by Rodgers et al. for ¹O₂ decay in heterogeneous media,[S2] the apparent decay rate constant (k_d) is described by Eq.S3 and is dependent on the composition of both phases.

$$k_d = \frac{(1 - f_m)k_{\text{aq}} + f_mk_{\text{pol}}K_{\text{eq}}}{(1 - f_m) + f_mK_{\text{eq}}} \quad \text{Eq.S3}$$

Where f_m and $(1-f_m)$ are the weighting coefficients equal to the volume fractions of the polymer and aqueous environments, respectively, and indicate the fraction of $^1\text{O}_2$ molecules that decay at each phase. K_{eq} is the equilibrium constant of $^1\text{O}_2$ between the two compartments or phases, expressed as the concentration of $^1\text{O}_2$ in the internal polymer phase divided by that in the external aqueous phase.

The values of f_m and k_{pol} can be estimated from the measured values of k_d in H_2O and D_2O for a wide range of K_{eq} values (Table S3). The chosen range for K_{eq} is given by the solubility of molecular oxygen in different polymers and in water.[S3] Of note, it is assumed that the solubility of $^1\text{O}_2$ in both microenvironments is similar to that of ground-state $^3\text{O}_2$. The values of $k_{\text{aq};\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ and $k_{\text{aq};\text{D}_2\text{O}}$ are taken as 0.303 and $0.0147 \mu\text{s}^{-1}$, respectively, in line with the values described in the literature.[S4]

Table S3. Estimated k_{pol} , f_m , and $(1-f_m)$ values for different K_{eq} (from 0.1 to 10).

	K_{eq}						
	10	5	2	1	0.5	0.2	0.1
$k_{\text{pol}} / \mu\text{s}^{-1}$	0.0087	0.0087	0.0087	0.0087	0.0087	0.0087	0.0087
f_m	0.972	0.986	0.994	0.997	0.999	0.999	1.000
$1-f_m$	0.028	0.014	0.006	0.003	0.001	0.001	<0.001

On one hand, k_{pol} value is almost independent with the K_{eq} in the studied range, resulting to a $^1\text{O}_2$ decay lifetime ($\tau_{\Delta;\text{pol}}$) of $116 \mu\text{s}$, which is similar to the apparent decay lifetime (τ_d) observed for the D_2O suspension. On the other hand, the f_m is larger than 0.97 for all the studied K_{eq} range, indicating that more than 97% of the $^1\text{O}_2$ molecules decay inside the polymer matrix and therefore this fraction cannot escape to the aqueous surroundings.

Figure S10. Determination of the ¹O₂ molecules that escape from the polymeric matrix by consumption of the fluorescent chemical acceptor tryptophan dissolved in D₂O. The photosensitizing clusters (0.3 g/L) were excited using the same 400 nm LED used for the photoantimicrobial studies (82 J/cm²). Prior the fluorescence determination of tryptophan, the CTE polymer clusters were removed by centrifugation (10000 rpm, 10 min) to avoid possible inner filter effect of those clusters on the fluorescence of the tryptophan. Tryptophan was chosen as the chemical acceptor for the following reasons: i) is fluorescent; ii) is highly-soluble in water at neutral pH with a logP of -1.6;^[S5] iii) does not absorb 405 nm photons; iv) is highly reactive against ¹O₂ ($k_r = 2.7 \times 10^7 \text{ M}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$);^[S6] and v) its oxidation products are not fluorescent. To avoid the entrapment of tryptophan inside the polymeric matrix, the tryptophan was added after the formation of the polymer clusters.

Figure S9 demonstrates a significant reduction in tryptophan fluorescence upon excitation of the polymer clusters (blue bar). The fluorescence quenching is much greater than in the absence of polymer clusters (compare blue and red bars) or in the absence of photoexcitation (compare blue and green bars). The effect of irradiation was also studied, showing no significant effect on the tryptophan fluorescence quenching (compare red and violet bars). Notably, incubation with the polymer phase reduces the tryptophan fluorescence, suggesting that some tryptophan molecules are located at the polymer surface and are removed during the centrifugation step. Therefore, the observed fluorescence quenching is attributed to tryptophan consumption in the D₂O by both ¹O₂ molecules that escaped from the polymeric matrix and those that reached the polymer surface.

Figure S11. Changes on the absorbance, fluorescence, τ_T and τ_Δ (top to bottom) over increasing the polymer concentration in water (H₂O).

Figure S12. Assessment of the cytotoxicity and phototoxicity of 1% dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) against *S. aureus*. $\lambda_{\text{Exc}} = 400 \text{ nm}$ (fluence 80 J/cm^2). (A): Bacterial growth of *S. aureus* incubated in PBS with 0% DMSO compared to 1% DMSO, with and without violet light irradiation. (b): Survival fraction of *S. aureus* incubated in PBS with 0% and 1% DMSO under violet light treatment. No relevant statistical differences (ns; $p \geq 0.05$) in phototoxicity were detected between the *S. aureus* cells incubated in PBS with 0% and 1% DMSO.

Figure S13. Emission spectra of the LED Par 64 Short V2 lamp Violet LED at 400 ± 8 nm (15.2 mW/cm²).

Figure S14. Assessment of the cytotoxicity of d-PBS. Bacterial growth of *S. aureus* in PBS and d-PBS without violet light treatment. The bacterial growth is expressed as Log₁₀(CFU/mL). No relevant statistical difference (ns; $p \geq 0.05$) in cytotoxicity is detected due to the replacement of PBS with d-PBS.

Figure S15. Photo-antimicrobial response of the CTEgen polymer in PBS and d-PBS. To differentiate the impact of the polymer from the endogenous photosensitizing molecules of *S. aureus*, the survival fraction incubated with 150 µg/mL of the polymer has been subtracted from the survival fraction without the polymer. This experiment has been repeated 18 independent times. Then, a statistical unpaired t-test has been performed, showing significant differences ($p < 0.0001$; ****) between the cells resuspended in PBS or d-PBS. The unpaired t-test analysis also provided the difference between means ("d-PBS" – "PBS") \pm SEM as -0.81 ± 0.18 with a 95% confidence interval of -1.17 to -0.45.

Figure S16. (Photo)-antimicrobial response of the polymer irradiated with violet light. (A): Survival curves of *Escherichia coli* with increasing concentrations of polymer. (B): Survival curves of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* with increasing concentrations of polymer. The non-irradiated dark control (light fluence of 0 J/cm²) is depicted with a black line and the photodynamic treatment is depicted with a red line (light fluence 80 J/cm²).

Figure S17. Interaction of the polymer aggregates with the three tested bacteria species. (A-C): Fluorescence spectra of a bacteria pellet (A: *S. aureus*, B: *E. coli*, C: *P. aeruginosa*) resuspended in fresh PBS, previously incubated with and without 0.15 g/L of the CTEgen polymer (blue and red lines, respectively). $\lambda_{Exc} = 355$ nm. Notably, the sharp band centered at 407 nm is assigned to the Raman scattering of H₂O. (D): Since the bacteria have endogenous fluorophores that cause autofluorescence, we assigned the CTEgen fluorescence component by subtracting the autofluorescence component of each type of bacteria.

References from Supporting Information

[S1] S. Cabani, G. Conti, L. Lepori, Thermodynamic study on aqueous dilute solutions of organic compounds. Part 2.—Cyclic ethers. *Trans. Faraday Soc.* **1971**, *67*, 1943-1950.

[S2] P.C. Lee, M.A.J. Rodgers, Singlet molecular oxygen in micellar systems. 1. Distribution equilibria between hydrophobic and hydrophilic compartments. *J. Phys. Chem.* **1983**, *87*, 4894-4898.

[S3] M.C. Celina, A. Quintana, Oxygen diffusivity and permeation through polymers at elevated temperature. *Polymer* **2018**, *150*, 326-342.

[S4] F. Wilkinson, W.P. Helman, A.B. Ross, Rate constants for the decay and reactions of the lowest electronically excited singlet state of molecular oxygen in solution. An expanded and revised compilation. *J. Phys. Chem. Ref. Data* **1995**, *24*, 663–677.

[S5] Z. Disdier, S. Savoye, R.V.H. Dagnelie, Effect of solutes structure and pH on the n-octanol/water partition coefficient of ionizable organic compounds, *Chemosphere* **2022**, *304*, 135155.

[S6] M.J. Davies, Singlet oxygen-mediated damage to proteins and its consequences. *Biochem. Biophys. Res. Commun.* **2003**, *305*, 761–770.